

DIGITAL ASSETS AND FINTECHS IN NIGERIA: THE IMPLICATION OF THE INVESTMENT AND SECURITIES ACT 2025 (ISA 2025)

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Introduction

Being nest to some of Africa’s leading Unicorns, Nigeria has proven to be one of Africa’s leading FinTech hubs with a bubbling market, driven by high mobile absorption and widespread demand for alternative, faster financial products and services by its youthful population that makes the larger percentage of her over 200 million population.

Digital assets, particularly cryptocurrencies, have played a central role in this growth, by enabling seamless cross-border payments, investment opportunities, and offering decentralised financial solutions to Nigerian citizens. For years, however, this innovation operated within a climate of regulatory uncertainty, marked by fragmented oversight and conflicting signals from regulators. It is notable that at some point in Nigeria’s financial journey, precisely in February 2021, the Central Bank of Nigeria (“CBN”) had barred financial institutions from crypto asset transactions.¹

The enactment of the **Investment and Securities Act 2025 (ISA 2025)**² represents a decisive policy shift. Rather than treating digital assets as an anomaly outside existing financial laws, the Act formally integrates them into Nigeria’s capital market framework by classifying certain digital assets as securities and placing them under the supervision of the **Securities and Exchange Commission (“SEC” or “the Commission”)**. This move signals Nigeria’s intention to transition from reactive regulation to structured market governance.

While the ISA 2025 aims to enhance investor protection, market integrity, and systemic stability, concerns remain that heavy compliance burdens and overlapping regulatory mandates, particularly with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), may constrain innovation while at the same time defeat the whole purpose of the industry which s decentralization. The challenge, therefore, lies in regulating digital assets in a manner that promotes confidence without stifling technological growth.

¹ However, in a circular issued on the 22 December 2023, the CBN permitted certain virtual asset service providers (VASP) activities and activities relating to cryptocurrencies and crypto assets, subject to new guidelines.

² Enacted in March 2025

Legal Classification of Digital Assets under ISA 2025

A defining feature of the ISA 2025 is its express recognition of digital assets and virtual assets within Nigeria's securities law framework. The Act expands the definition of securities to include investment instruments issued, recorded, or transferred using distributed ledger or blockchain technology, where such instruments exhibit investment characteristics.³ This effectively brings cryptocurrencies, tokens, and similar digital instruments, when used for investment purposes, within the regulatory ambit of securities law.

The legal consequence of this classification is novel in Nigeria. Digital asset issuers, exchanges, custodians, and intermediaries are now subject to registration, licensing, disclosure, and capital requirements applicable to capital market operators.⁴ Activities such as token offerings by blockchain developers, crypto exchanges, and digital asset custody are no longer legally neutral innovations but regulated financial services requiring SEC approval.

The ISA 2025 now consolidates the SEC's jurisdiction over digital assets classified as securities, empowering it to regulate issuance, trading platforms, market conduct, and investor protection mechanisms. This statutory clarity addresses previous ambiguity, where regulatory authority oscillated between the SEC's investment mandate and the CBN's monetary and payment-system concerns. While this classification strengthens legal certainty, it also raises questions about proportionality, regulatory overlap, and the future balance between financial innovation and oversight in Nigeria's digital economy.

Compliance Obligations for FinTech and Digital Asset Firms

With the classification of certain digital assets as securities under the Investment and Securities Act 2025 (ISA 2025), FinTech firms operating in this space are now subject

³ Section 357, ISA 2025

⁴ On Friday 16th January 2026, the Commission unveiled a revised capital framework to replace the 2015 structure, giving operators until June 30, 2027 to comply. The new minimum capital requirements for operators in Nigeria's capital market, which provides the thresholds for stockbrokers, dealers, fund managers, issuing houses, and digital asset companies establishes that Digital Assets Exchange (DAX) and Digital Assets Custodian: Minimum capital is raised from N500 million to N2 billion; Digital Assets Offering Platform (DAOP): Requirement increased from N500 million to N1 billion; Ancillary Virtual Assets Service Providers (AVASPs): Newly introduced with a minimum capital of N300 million; Digital Assets Intermediary (DAI): Required to hold N500 million (newly introduced); Digital Assets Platform Operators (DAPOs), including token issuers: Minimum capital set at N500 million (newly introduced); Real-world Assets Tokenization and Offering Platforms (RATOP): Capital requirement pegged at N1 billion (newly introduced). See also <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2026/01/sec-raises-capital-base-for-market-operators-gives-18-months-to-comply/> Last accessed 27th January 2026

to the full spectrum of capital market compliance obligations. Digital asset exchanges, token issuers, custodians, and other intermediaries must register with and obtain licences from the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) before commencing operations. Operating without registration exposes firms to administrative sanctions, fines, and potential criminal liability under the Act.⁵

Beyond licensing, the ISA 2025 imposes disclosure and transparency requirements aimed at investor protection. Firms are hence required to provide accurate information on the nature of digital assets offered, enlist associated risks, spell out governance structures, and state financial standing.⁶ This mirrors traditional securities regulation and reflects a policy decision to treat digital asset investors similarly to conventional capital market participants.

Capital adequacy requirements represent a major compliance shift. SEC rules made pursuant to Section 313 of the ISA 2025 prescribe substantial minimum paid-up capital thresholds, particularly for Digital Asset Exchanges (DAEs) and custodians, in order to ensure market stability and reduce systemic risk. Additionally, firms must comply with ongoing obligations relating to corporate governance, anti-money laundering (AML), and consumer protection, aligning digital asset operations with Nigeria's broader financial regulatory framework.

Capitalisation of the Digital Asset Exchanges

One of the most controversial aspects of Nigeria's digital asset regulation is the SEC's imposition of high minimum capital requirements, reportedly reaching up to ₦2 billion for Digital Asset Exchanges.⁷ It can be argued that these thresholds are intended to ensure that only financially sound operators manage investor funds, thereby reducing the risk of market collapse, fraud, and insolvency, however, they exist thoughts around whether the market has willing investors to pull in such capitals as it appears most dealers in the market are not properly structured.

In other words, these requirements raise serious concerns for startups, MSMEs, and early-stage FinTech innovators, many of whom lack access to such capital despite possessing viable and innovative business models. The result is a regulatory

⁵ Section 84(7), ISA 2025

⁶ Sections 162–165

⁷ <https://nairametrics.com/2026/01/16/sec-raises-capital-requirement-for-crypto-exchanges-in-nigeria-to-n2-billion/>

environment that may favour well-funded incumbents while excluding smaller, local players who have historically driven innovation in Nigeria's FinTech ecosystem.

The capitalization regime also has its own implications for foreign market entry in the industry. While high thresholds may deter speculative or poorly regulated foreign operators, they may also discourage legitimate international FinTech firms seeking to test the Nigerian market as many may not be willing to pull in such quantum of funds in investment for a test. This creates a delicate policy tension, which is that, while strong capital requirements promote market confidence and investor protection, excessive thresholds risk pushing innovation offshore or into informal markets, undermining Nigeria's ambition to remain a leading digital finance hub in Africa.

Regulatory Coordination between SEC and CBN

Regulatory oversight of digital assets and FinTech activities in Nigeria has historically suffered from overlapping mandates between the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to regulate the sector.

The CBN, empowered under the **Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007** and the **Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020**, had over time attempted to assume the responsibility of coordinating digital assets. Ordinarily, CBN is meant to regulate monetary policy, payment systems, and financial institutions, however, it has in recent times concerned itself around crypto-assets especially as it touches financial stability, money laundering, terrorism financing, and consumer protection, which informed its restrictive posture, including the 2021 circular limiting banks' exposure to crypto-related businesses.⁸

Conversely, the SEC, pursuant to the Investments and Securities Act (ISA), asserts jurisdiction over digital assets that qualify as securities or investment products. In 2020, under the ISA, 2007, SEC formally classified crypto-assets as securities unless proven otherwise, bringing them under its regulatory ambit. A query around this then becomes whether all crypto-assets qualify as securities and why the burden of disproving the security nature of a digital-currency should depend on the owners instead of there being a criteria that works independently to determine what crypto-assets qualify as securities.

The enactment of the Investments and Securities Act 2025 signals a shift toward clearer regulatory coordination. The Act strengthens the Commission's authority over virtual assets, digital investment schemes, and capital market operators, while recognizing the

⁸ See the Guidelines on Operations of Bank Accounts for Virtual Assets Service Providers (VASPs) of December 22, 2023

CBN's role in payment systems and banking supervision.⁹ When read alongside BOFIA 2020, a dual-regulatory framework emerges; and it is one that encourages functional collaboration rather than institutional conflict.

It then becomes safe to mention that effective harmonization will greatly depend on inter-agency guidelines, joint regulatory legal and procedural frameworks, and efficient information-sharing schemes that will ensure regulatory certainty for FinTech and digital asset operators.

Taxation and Compliance Burden

The taxation of crypto and digital asset transactions in Nigeria remains an evolving area, with compliance obligations posing significant challenges for operators.

Under the **Tax Act 2025**, taxable supplies attract 7.5% Value Added Tax,¹⁰ and recent guidance from tax authorities suggests that certain digital transaction, particularly platform fees and intermediary services, may fall within the VAT net. However, ambiguity persists regarding whether peer-to-peer crypto transactions constitute taxable supplies.

Beyond VAT, FinTech and crypto-related firms also face corporate income tax obligations under the same Tax Act 2025, as well as potential capital gains tax exposure where digital assets are treated as chargeable assets.

Compliance costs extend beyond taxation. Licensing fees, reporting requirements, AML/CFT obligations under the Money Laundering (Prevention and Prohibition) Act 2022, and data protection compliance under the Nigeria Data Protection Act 2023 significantly increase operational burdens.

In response, many FinTech firms have adopted adaptive compliance strategies, including compliance outsourcing, RegTech solutions, regulatory sandboxes and proactive engagement with regulators. While these measures mitigate risk, they also underscore the need for clearer, harmonised, and innovation-friendly regulatory policies.

⁹ Section 357, ISA

¹⁰ Section 147, Tax Act

Conclusion and Recommendations

Nigeria's evolving digital economy requires a careful balance between innovation and regulation. The ISA 2025 represents a positive shift toward structured oversight of digital assets, but effective regulation must run with the spirit that sustainable growth is the "crown of glory" any policy or regulation should work towards attaining.

Furthermore, it is hence noteworthy that, to achieve sustainable growth, regulators should:

- a. Strengthen inter-agency coordination between the SEC, CBN, FCCPC, and the Nigerian tax authorities.
- b. Adopt graduated compliance frameworks for startups and emerging FinTech firms.
- c. Expand the use of regulatory sandboxes to encourage innovation while managing associated risks.
- d. Issue clearer guidance on taxation and asset classification to reduce compliance uncertainty.
- e. Establish a more relatable criteria to make for asset classification especially as it concerns securities.

The use of policies and regulations will be very helpful in enabling the key regulators of the Financial Industry bring to life the potentials of ISA 2025, and regulators are strongly advised to maximise this.